

**THE IMPORTANCE OF INTENSIVE LISTENING WHILE
TEACHING LANGUAGE**

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Abstract. *Listening skills play a pivotal role in language acquisition and effective communication, making them a fundamental aspect of language education. Intensive listening involves focused and deliberate efforts to comprehend spoken language, often through concentrated exposure to authentic audio materials or teacher-led activities. This paper highlights the importance of intensive listening while teaching language.*

Keywords: *intensive, listening, importance, hearing. distinctive, spoken.*

Annotatsiya. *Tinglash ko'nikmalari tilni o'zlashtirish va samarali muloqotda muhim rol o'ynaydi va ularni til ta'limning asosiy jihati ga aylantiradi. Intensiv tinglash ko'nikmasi, ko'pincha haqiqiy audio materiallarga diqqatni jamlangan holda ta'sir qilish yoki o'qituvchi tomonidan olib boriladigan tadbirlardan iborat bo'lgan og'zaki tilni tushunish uchun yo'naltirilgan harakatlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu maqolada til o'rgatish jarayonida tinglab tushunish ko'nikmasining ahamiyati yoritib berilgan.*

Аннотация. *Навыки аудирования играют ключевую роль в овладении языком и эффективном общении, что делает их фундаментальным аспектом языкового образования. Интенсивное аудирование предполагает целенаправленные и целенаправленные усилия по пониманию разговорной речи, часто посредством концентрированного воздействия аутентичных аудиоматериалов или занятий под руководством учителя. В этой статье подчеркивается важность интенсивного слушания во время обучения языку.*

Kalit so'zlar: *intensiv, tinglash, muhimlik, eshitish. o'ziga xos, gapirilgan.*
Ключевые слова: интенсивный, слушание, важность, слух. характерный, разговорный

“Listening is a fundamental language skill,
but it is often ignored by foreign and
second language teachers “
Rebeccal.

Listening is a cornerstone skill in language acquisition, forming the bedrock for effective communication and language proficiency. Among the various approaches to honing this skill, intensive listening emerges as a focused and strategic method designed to elevate students' overall listening proficiency. Intensive listening is a purposeful and detailed engagement with spoken language. It involves a concentrated effort to discern specific linguistic elements such as vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar, and contextual nuances. Intensive listening serves as a vehicle for expanding students' vocabulary. By closely attending to pronunciation and contextual usage, learners gain a deeper understanding of word meanings and applications. Focused attention on spoken sentences during intensive listening sharpens students' comprehension of grammatical structures and syntax, contributing to enhanced grammatical proficiency. The deliberate emphasis on pronunciation in intensive listening allows students to refine their own speaking skills by mimicking native speakers' intonation, rhythm, and articulation. Intensive listening cultivates critical thinking as students analyze spoken language for specific details. This skill is indispensable for deciphering complex information, identifying key points, and making informed inferences.

Listening, as we know, is the skill of understanding spoken language. Listening is an essential skill, present in most of the activities we carry out throughout our lives. We listen to a wide variety of things, for example; what someone says during a conversation, face to face or on the telephone; announcements giving information, for example, at an airport or railway station; the weather forecast on the radio; professional advice, for example, at the doctor’s, in the bank; instructions, for example, on how to use a photocopier or other machinery; directions. Listening is a psychological phenomenon, which takes place on a cognitive level inside people’s heads, and a social phenomenon, which develops interactively between people and the environment surrounding them. It considers listening as a complex process, which needs to be understood in order to teach it, and subsequently, evaluate it before integrating it with phonological aspects and with the skill of speaking.

It has taken many years to give the listening skill the importance it deserves in second and foreign language learning among the teaching profession. Rivers claimed, “Speaking does not of itself constitute communication unless what is said is comprehended by another person. Teaching the comprehension of spoken speech is therefore a primary importance of the communication aim is to be reached”. However, Morley notes, “perhaps an assumption that listening is a reflex, a little like breathing - listening seldom receives overt teaching attention in one’s native language – has marked the importance and complexity of listening with understanding in a nonnative language”. Contrary to what everybody thinks about foreign language learning, listening competence is wider than speaking competence. This is the reason why; recently, the language teaching profession has brought into focus on listening comprehension. According to Nunan listening is a six-staged process, consisting of :

- Hearing,
- Attending,
- Understanding,
- Remembering,
- Evaluating
- Responding.

These stages occur in sequence and rapid succession. The first one is Hearing and has to do with the response caused by sound waves stimulating the sensory receptors of the ear; hearing is the perception of sound, not necessarily paying attention, you must hear to listen, but you need not listen to hear. For this, we have Attention. It refers to a selection that our brain focuses on. The brain screens stimuli and permits only a select few to come into focus. The third stage is Understanding, which consists of analyzing the meaning of what we have heard and understanding symbols we have seen and heard. We must analyze the stimuli we have perceived. Symbolic stimuli are not only words, they can be sounds like applause or even sights, like a blue uniform that have symbolic meanings as well. To do this, we have to stay in the right context and understand the intended meaning. The meaning attached to these symbols is a function of our past associations and of the context in which the symbols occur for successful interpersonal communication: the listener must understand the intended meaning and the context assumed by the sender. After following with the next stage, it is necessary to make a remark: as it has mentioned previously, the background knowledge is important and people have to take into account several points: general factual information, local factual information, socio-cultural knowledge and knowledge of context. With these factors, the information will be correctly received. The next step, Remembering, is an important Listening process because it means that an

individual, in addition to receiving and interpreting the message, has also added it to the mind's storage bank, which means that the information will be remembered in our mind. But just as our attention is selective, so too is our memory, what is remembered may be quite different from what was originally heard or seen. In the penultimate stage, Evaluating, the listener evaluates the message that has been received. It is at this point when active listeners weigh evidence, sort fact from opinion and determine the presence or absence of bias or prejudice in a message. The effective listener makes sure that he or she does not begin this activity too soon, as beginning this stage of the process before a message is completed results in no longer hearing and attending to the incoming message and, as a result, the Listening process ceases. Finally, we have Responding, a stage in which, according to the response, the speaker checks if the message has been received correctly. This stage requires that the receiver complete the process through verbal or non verbal feedback, because the speaker has no other way to determine if a message has been received. Therefore, it is sometimes complicated as we do not have the opportunity to go back and check comprehension.

Intensive listening involves focusing on specific details of spoken language. It requires careful attention to understand specific words, phrases, or expressions used by the speaker. Intensive listening demands focused attention on the speaker's words, often involving repeated listening to grasp the details accurately. The listener aims to understand specific information, such as vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, or specific content details. Intensive listening involves a deep analysis of the language being used, including sentence structures, idiomatic expressions, and nuances. It is often text-based, involving listening to recorded materials, lectures, or conversations to analyze and comprehend the language used. Intensive listening helps learners expand their vocabulary by paying close attention to the pronunciation, usage, and meaning of specific words. In academic or professional settings, intensive listening is crucial for understanding specific content details, instructions, or information conveyed in spoken form. Listening to a language learning podcast and focusing on the pronunciation and usage of new vocabulary. Analyzing a recorded lecture to understand the application of specific grammatical structures.

The goal in intensive listening is to learn new language – in spoken form. A second goal in some cases might be to learn some content. Intensive listening takes time, but because you need concentration, you should only do it for short periods of time. You'll probably have a variety of tasks to do if you do intensive listening in an English class. And ideally, but not as important as in the case of extensive listening, the content should be interesting to you.

Tips for Intensive Listening to Learn English:

- Focus on form, not content.
- Listen to short video or audio recordings.
- Listen to difficult / challenging content.
- Focus on form, not content:
- Listen carefully for details and language use, not main ideas.
- Use the video or audio recording to help you learn new language.
- If possible, choose content that is interesting to you.
- Listen with support activities from your teacher or that you create. Much of your

intensive listening work might be done in class.

Intensive listening takes a lot of your effort and energy, but it's worth it. During intensive listening, the learner listens very carefully. For example, while listening to directions the listener listens with full concentration. Such listening

short and has a special task or worksheet designed on it. There is some amount of challenge so that the learner feels motivated to complete the task. It is through the completion of this task that the learner gets practice in specific listening skills. The intensive listening practice takes place in class and should be so designed that it is practical, easy to administer, and can be completed within the time limit of a lesson. The listening tasks are effective if the learners have a well-designed, interesting and carefully graded activity to complete. Some of these tasks can be to express agreement or disagreement, take notes, make a picture or diagram according to instructions or answer questions. The task which is set on a worksheet prepares the learner for the kind of information to expect and how to react to it. It helps in contextualizing and aids comprehension. Very often the listening task is based on filling in diagrams, grids, maps and tables. It is important to bear in mind that these grids etc. are simple and do not become overelaborate.

Intensive listening serves as a catalyst for nuanced comprehension, allowing students to delve into the intricate layers of vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. By zooming in on specific language elements, students not only grasp the meaning of words and sentences but also hone their ability to discern contextual nuances and cultural subtleties. This depth of understanding lays the foundation for language proficiency that transcends basic communication.

One of the distinctive features of intensive listening lies in its cultivation of critical thinking skills. As students actively dissect spoken language for specific details, they learn to analyze, evaluate, and infer meaning. This skill set extends beyond the realm of language learning, empowering students to approach academic and professional challenges with a discerning and analytical mindset.

All in all, the role of intensive listening in developing students' listening skills emerges not only as an educational strategy but as a transformative force in language education. It is a journey that goes beyond the surface, guiding students to unravel the intricacies of spoken language, fostering critical thinking, and paving the way for a lifelong appreciation and mastery of effective communication. As we navigate the evolving landscape of language education, the role of intensive listening stands tall, steering students toward a future where language is not just a tool but a skill mastered with depth and precision.

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